

HyDelta 3

WP5B – Technology and safety in the hydrogen network – Hydrogen leakages and control measures

D5b.1+2 Risks of hydrogen leakages // Preventive and corrective measures

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Summary

Gas leaks in a natural gas distribution network cannot be ruled out. The causes of these gas leaks are diverse and so are the quantity and distribution of the gas that is released. The aim of this work package is to gain an insight into the differences and similarities in the safety risks when approaching and repairing a hydrogen leak compared to a natural gas leak. The research focuses on the actions of the technician and which (additional) practical measures are necessary when approaching and repairing a hydrogen leak.

The following research questions are central to this study;

- What are the risks of a hydrogen leak in the distribution network at different pressures in realistic practical situations?
- What mitigating measures should a technician implement to secure and repair a hydrogen leak?

In order to answer the main questions, literature research was conducted into the origin of leaks, the size of the leak, the dangers of these leaks and their effects. Depending on the situation of the network (for example 8 bar network or 100 mbar network) there are various hazards such as the hazard of free flow, the possibility of ignition and suffocation. The effects of gas leaks were determined for six predetermined situations, whereby the effects of hydrogen leaks were compared with the effects of natural gas leaks.

Due to the lower ignition energy, the wider flammability limits, the higher outflow rate and higher flame speed, the risks in the event of a hydrogen leak are higher than in the event of a natural gas leak.

The current level of knowledge regarding the origin of leaks, the size of the leak, the hazards of these leaks and their effects are well secured in the work instructions of the VIAG (general Dutch safety instructions for distribution system companies and their subcontractors). Based on the present research, it appears that it is possible to approach and repair hydrogen leaks in a safe manner. The work instructions as used for the approach and repair of natural gas leaks will have to be adjusted. In addition, additional mitigating measures are necessary compared to natural gas. The most important adjustments in work instructions and the most important measures are ;

- Approaching a leak with a thermal imaging camera.
- Applying greater safety distances in the event of medium and large gas leaks.
- After depressurizing, the insulated pipe section must be flushed with nitrogen.
- Temporary repairs must not be carried out under gas pressure.
- If air has entered the gas pipe during repair, it must be flushed with nitrogen.
- Technicians who are going to work on a hydrogen network will need additional instruction. Working with hydrogen requires a different approach than working with natural gas. Another aspect for the safety of the work is the mentality of the technician. Hydrogen is in many aspects a more dangerous gas than natural gas and can lead to incidents more quickly when performing the same actions as done with natural gas. Hydrogen will also be used less frequently in the start-up phase. Little or no experience is gained, which means that errors occur more quickly. There is a chance that a technician will rely on the experiences with natural gas and therefore not carry out the work safely.
- Before the (excavation) work begins, the pipe must first be depressurized and degassed. Locating can still be carried out safely up to gas percentages below 10% LFL (0.4 vol.-% H₂). Digging in hydrogen-saturated soil is a risk that cannot be assessed at this time because research is lacking. When degassing, it must always be flushed with nitrogen. In the event of

excavation damage, this is necessary from both sides¹ from the interruption to the leak. Above ground, the leak size cannot be estimated and the chance of ignition is high.

- When repairing a leak that enters a building, the supply must first be shut off at an appropriate distance. It is also advisable to measure the gas concentration(s) in nearby buildings. This is in accordance with the procedure for natural gas.
- The safety distances in case of accumulation in buildings are determined in particular by the consequences of a possible explosion. At hydrogen concentrations in a building above 20 vol%, flying glass can cause injury 50 to 70 meters from the facade. For natural gas, this distance is a maximum of 40 meters.
- When a gas cloud ignites in the open air, it has been experimentally determined that the shock wave experienced remains relatively limited even at higher gas flow rates (approximately 6,000 m³/h). The heat radiation of a hydrogen fire is lower than a natural gas fire.
- When restoring the gas supply, the pipe must first be flushed with nitrogen if air has been able to enter the pipe. This can be done when pipe sections, connections or appendages have been replaced.
- When restoring the gas supply, the greatest hazard with natural gas is an unprotected cooking appliance that can (in exceptional circumstances) cause an explosive mixture in a kitchen. When converting to hydrogen, all combustion appliances must be replaced or modified. New appliances are equipped with a protection against the escape of unburned gas. When restoring the gas supply, no similar risks can arise as with natural gas.
- When carrying out repair and maintenance work, gas detection equipment with at least an H₂ and O₂ sensor should be worn.

Based on the research carried out, the following recommendations are made:

- Performing additional calculations regarding the ignition of a gas cloud in free space at small(er) flow rates or performing additional tests in line with the area of interest of this report.
- Conducting (practical) research into excavation work in hydrogen-saturated soil.
- Provide proper training to technicians who are going to work on a hydrogen network and ensure that they take refresher courses regularly if experience with hydrogen cannot be gained frequently.

¹ With a meshed network, more interruptions may be necessary. In those situations it is necessary to flush with nitrogen from every interruption towards the leak.

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1 Introduction

1.1 General

This research was conducted within the framework of the national research programme HyDelta . This programme focuses on the safe integration of hydrogen into the existing infrastructure for gas transport and gas distribution and aims to remove barriers for innovative hydrogen projects. The entire research programme is divided into work packages. For an explanation of the various work packages, see www.hydelta.nl

1.2 Objective

The aim of this study is to gain insight into the differences and similarities in safety risks when approaching and repairing a hydrogen leak compared to a natural gas leak. This literature study focuses on the technician and which (additional) practical measures are necessary when approaching and repairing a hydrogen leak.

1.3 Main questions

- What are the risks of a hydrogen leak in the distribution network at different pressures in realistic practical situations?
- What mitigating measures should a technician implement to secure and repair a hydrogen leak?

To answer the main questions, research has been conducted into the origin of leaks, the size of the leaks, the dangers of these leaks and their effects. The relationship between these is shown below.

1.4 Relationship between the terms

A leak can lead to a hazard (fire, explosion or suffocation). The hazard affects the technician when he is exposed to it when approaching and repairing a leak;

- Fire – injury
- Explosion – injury
- Suffocation – suffocation

The probability of the hazard occurring and the magnitude of the effect are determined by the degree of outflow and the situation in which the outflow occurs. They are therefore decisive for the risk. This is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview situations

Type of leak	Leak size	Danger	Effect
The situation/cause of the leak	Distinction in; Small (< 0.05 m ³ /h) medium (< 50 m ³ /h) and large (> 50m ³ /h) See H4 for further explanation.	Danger (fire/explosion/suffocation) that could occur in this situation with this leak size	Effect of the hazard to the technician when approaching the leak and repairing it

The possible effect (when this is more serious than with natural gas) gives rise to taking additional or different measures to protect the technician.

1.5 Principles and preconditions

A number of starting points and boundary conditions have been established for this research. These are shown below.

External and internal leaks

The hazards and risks relate to the technician who detects and/or repairs an external leak. The effects of accumulation in buildings or structures are included. However, the effects of internal leaks are not part of this study.

LFL, LEL and lower flammability limit

In this report, the abbreviation LFL is used for the lower flammability limit of a gas. The term LEL could also have been used here. This latter abbreviation is in line with the Dutch and European standards in use. These standards do not distinguish between LEL (lower explosion limit) and LFL (lower flammability limit), which is why this distinction is not made in this report.

LEL and LFL refer to the lower flammability limit. Below the lower flammability limit, there is insufficient fuel to sustain a combustion reaction. Above the lower flammability limit, a mixture of gas and air can be ignited. For hydrogen, the lower flammability limit is 4 vol% hydrogen in air, for natural gas this value is 5.8 vol%. Gas detection equipment (personal protective equipment) usually gives a signal when 10% of the lower flammability limit is reached (the display shows 10% LEL). In the event of a gas leak, a gas cloud will never have a homogeneous concentration. At the outlet, the gas concentration is always 100%, this concentration decreases towards the edges of the gas cloud.

2 Causes of leaks

Gas leaks can occur in various ways. When mapping these causes the Nestor data was used. This is the system in which all failures of the Dutch network operators are registered. Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the five most common causes of failures in main lines and service lines where the result was a gas smell or gas leak. In the case of the service lines, only the components that are located outside a building were considered. Interviews were also held with technicians and managers of the network operators (Stedin , Enexis , Liander and Cogas) to determine whether there are other causes or effects of leaks that can be identified that occur in the current natural gas network. These causes were compared with the causes described in Nestor. For each cause, the expected leak size is indicated (small/medium/large). An explanation of these leak rates and their effects are described in chapter 3.

The interviews also mentioned a number of aspects that are not relevant to answering the research questions, but are useful to include in this report. See Appendix B for this.

Figure 1: The top 5 causes of main line failures over the past years (Source: Nestor)

Figure 2: The top 5 causes of service line failures (parts outside the facade) over the past years (Source: Nestor)

2.1 Corrosion/ageing

The most common cause of main line leaks is corrosion and/or aging of pipes and components. Because pipes and components lie in the ground for a long period of time, they can slowly be affected by the environment.

When switching to hydrogen, pipes will still age and corrode. Hydrogen has only a limited influence on this. Even when using hydrogen, small leaks will always occur due to ageing or corrosion. If a leak occurs, up to three times more hydrogen can flow out due to the other properties of hydrogen. Leaks due to corrosion or ageing start as a small leak and can slowly increase in size to a medium-sized leak.

2.1.1 Hydrogen embrittlement

The term hydrogen embrittlement is often mentioned as a form of material degradation in steel hydrogen pipes. Hydrogen penetration into the steel and the attack of steel by hydrogen only occurs at temperatures above 300°C [1]. Hydrogen can cause an acceleration of crack growth in steel. This can only happen if (hairline) cracks have developed in a pipe and the hydrogen then causes a limited acceleration of the crack growth compared to the natural growth. The research results as described in “*Comparing the risk of third-party excavation damage between natural gas* [2]” do not give any reason to avoid the use of steel pipes in a hydrogen network. Hydrogen embrittlement will therefore not be included in this study.

2.2 Excavation damage

Another important cause of leaks in main and connection pipes is excavation damage. The number of excavation damages to main pipes has remained approximately the same in recent years (an average of 1,100 per year). For service lines, the number of excavation damages with gas odor or gas leakage is approximately 3,000 per year). Excavation damage often involves damage caused by mechanical excavation. Mechanical damage, both in main pipes and in service lines often results in large openings in the pipe (or the pipe is even completely ruptured). As a result, excavation damage will quickly lead to a large leak in practice. This is because with an 8 bar pipe, a leak size of 1.6 mm is sufficient to obtain an outflow of more than 50 m³/h and with 100 mbar this applies to a hole of 6 mm or more (see Table 3). In the case of excavation damage, the leak opening that occurs is usually many times larger.

In the event of excavation damage, the leakage rate is three times higher for a hydrogen pipeline compared to a natural gas pipeline. The risks with hydrogen are greater than with natural gas. This is because the chance of ignition is greater due to the wider flammability limits and less ignition energy is required for larger gas concentrations. In addition, the effect of an ignition is greater because the flame speed of hydrogen is higher. This can cause a larger pressure wave.

2.3 Installation errors

There are a legion of possible sources of leakage conceivable as a result of installation errors. Installation errors include poorly tightened caps of a connection saddle, connections in PE without support bushings and an incorrect mirror weld connection. The interviews showed that in most cases this cause leads to a small or medium leakage and in exceptional cases it can also be a large leakage.

2.4 Ground movement

Ground movement can cause pipes to be pulled out of a connection. The interviews and data from the Safety Indicator ² showed that in the case of main pipes, with non- tensile connections, this is mainly caused by the gas pipe being washed under by a leaking water pipe. The result of this type of leakage is a large leak. In service lines, ground movements can cause a pipe to be pulled out of its connection. This causes a medium to large leak.

2.5 Point load

A point load causes leaks in PE pipes if a stone or other sharp object is pressed onto a PE pipe. This load leads to tensions in the material and can cause cracks to form. This slow process results in a small or medium leak.

2.6 Overloaded electrical cable

Overloading of electrical cables can cause high temperatures. This temperature is high enough to melt a plastic pipe. The overload can also form a source of ignition. This type of leak is usually characterized by a medium to large leakage.

2.7 Permeation

Permeation is the effect that mainly occurs in plastic pipes where a gas penetrates the pipe wall by a natural process. The amount of hydrogen that 'leaks' by permeation is the largest in first generation PE pipes. Approximately 10.3 m³/(km/year) leaks [3]. In practice, this means that a PE pipe of 1 km leaks approximately 0.02 liters of hydrogen per hour. These are minimum values compared to permitted leak sizes according to NEN7244 (< 5 L/h for main pipes). For this reason, permeation is not considered further in this report.

²The Safety Indicator is a measure of the safety of a Dutch gas distribution network. The lower the indicator, the safer the network.

3 Spread of a leakage

3.1 Above ground

Small hydrogen leakages will, as with small natural gas leakages, quickly mix with the air present in the environment and will not be able to form flammable mixtures in the open air. The study “Flaring and Venting” [4] has identified the size of gas plumes at four flow rates (three calculated and one estimated). Based on this report, Table 2 is drawn up.

Table 2 Size of plumes of unburned hydrogen (at 1.5 m/s crosswind)

	H ₂ – 300 m ³ /h		H ₂ – 100 m ³ /h		H ₂ – 50 m ³ /h		H ₂ – 10 m ³ /h	
	100% LFL	10% LFL	100% LFL	10% LFL	100% LFL	10% LFL	100% LFL	10% LFL
Horizontal plume length (m)	4.5	32	4.4	20	about 3	about 16	1.5	5.5
Vertical plume length (m)	1.7	4.5	1,7	2.6	-	-	0.20	0.42
Volume of plume (m ³)	1,2	75	0.33	17	about 0.14	-	0.014	0.33
Leakage size	large		large		medium		medium	

3.2 Underground

If a pipe leaks underground, the gas will find its way to the top (the density is less than air). However, the gas does not always go straight up. The gas will seek the path of least resistance. If there is an opening (for example, a space around the pipe), the gas will move through this cavity. The interviews also show that there are many possibilities in which gas can escape via another route. For example, leaking gas can end up in sewers, ducts for telecom cables or cable protection bands (wide plastic flaps, sometimes even folded double, creating a hollow space). In some cases, this appears to be harmless, but in other cases, the gas can enter a closed space via, for example, a sewer or a poorly sealed facade duct. This includes large sewer systems, distribution boxes for electricity or telecom and crawl spaces. Facade ducts (of gas pipes or other infrastructure) are not always finished gas-tight, which means that the leaking gas can easily enter a building. Internal leaks are outside the scope of this project, but leakages close to a facade can cause gas to enter a crawl space.

The distribution of hydrogen through the soil is approximately equal to the distribution of natural gas in the soil. This is the result of a study [5] by performing practical tests and calculations. With a constant leak opening, the leakage rate was a factor of 2.4 higher (50 l/h hydrogen versus 20.2 l/h natural gas). However, this larger quantity of leak gas led to lower concentrations in the soil. The hydrogen therefore spreads more quickly through the assessed soil, but over approximately the same surface area.

3.3 To a closed space

If an enclosed space (such as a crawl space) is filled with a flammable concentration of gas, this can create a dangerous situation. In some cases, crawl spaces are poorly ventilated and ignition sources may be present, such as the air supply of an open fireplace. The effect is then usually an explosion. The Dutch Institute for Public Safety (NIPV) states in the report [6] on hydrogen incidents in enclosed spaces that most hydrogen explosions are deflagrations. In other words, the speed of the flame front of the explosion is lower than the speed of sound. A deflagration can turn into a detonation if the hydrogen burns so quickly that the speed of the flame front becomes greater than the speed of

sound in the mixture. This leads to overpressures that in the "ideal" scenario can increase to a factor of 20 times greater than the ambient pressure. Many factors are important here, such as the location of the ignition source in relation to the space, but also the number of obstacles in the space. An ignition at the end of a space produces a higher pressure than ignition in the middle of a space. The presence of many obstacles can cause a lot of turbulence, which causes a higher combustion rate and therefore higher pressure.

In order to cause a detonation in a space, the hydrogen concentration in a cloud must be at least 18.5 vol.-% [7]. If the concentration is lower, there can be no transition from deflagration to detonation, because the detonation cannot sustain itself. In addition, it is important that pressure can be built up. When breaking a window, for example, the pressure drops and the detonation will be less able to be sustained.

It is very difficult to predict the effects of an ignition of a gas accumulation, because this depends on many different (environmental) factors. However, two studies in the context of Hy4Heat have drawn approximately the same conclusions. The first study [7] based its conclusions on calculation models and the other study [8] used practical tests.

The conclusion of both studies is that the effects of ignition of hydrogen up to 15 vol.-% are smaller than with natural gas. In the case of ignition of a hydrogen concentration between 15 and 20 vol.-%, the effects are approximately comparable to the effects of ignition of a natural gas mixture between 8 and 12 vol.-%. Above 20 vol.-% hydrogen, the effects become increasingly greater.

In the event of ignition of a gas mixture in a building, the building can collapse. The pressure wave, fireball, heat and collapsing building parts can cause injury to people inside the building. This study focuses on injuries to technicians who are outside a building. The greatest risk of injury on the outside of a building is caused by flying glass in the event of an explosion in a building due to incoming leaking gas. In the event of ignition of natural gas, the flying glass has a maximum range of between 25 and 40 metres. For hydrogen, this distance is much greater, namely up to 50 to 70 metres at a hydrogen concentration of 25 vol.-% (and possibly even greater for higher concentrations). See Figure 3 for the relationship between distance and gas concentration. Flying glass is not the only hazard that can cause injury; the consequences of heat radiation and a pressure wave were also included in the study [7]. However, the areas of both of these effects are smaller than the area of the flying glass, see Figure 4.

Other flying parts of the building (window frames, debris, etc.) can also cause injury to people outside the building, but these parts will spread over a shorter distance than flying glass. These heavier building parts are not blown away as far, but can lead to more serious injuries. In chapter 5 an alternative consideration of safety distances is given in relation to glass damage. This consideration results in a safety distance of 50 metres as a result of overpressure to the environment.

Figure 3: The distance that glass flies away during an ignition in a confined space with natural gas and hydrogen [7].

Figure 4: Areas outside a building in which injury is likely to occur in the event of a hydrogen ignition in a building [7]

4 Effects of different leakage rates

A distinction is made between small, medium-sized and large leakages, also referred to in this report as a 'type of leak'. The leakage rates for these three descriptions have been determined by the Expert Assessment Group. A small leak (up to 0.05 m³/h) is usually noticed during above-ground leak detection. A medium-sized leak (0.05 – 50m³/h) can be detected both by above-ground leak detection and by gas smell notifications. Large leaks (>50 m³/h) are detected by gas smell notifications, spraying soil, excavation damage reports and/or malfunctions at customers.

The leakage rate depends on the leakage opening and the mains pressure. Table 3 has been drawn up to provide insight into which leakage opening corresponds to which type of leak at the various network pressures. A circular leakage opening has been used as a starting point.

In this chapter, the previously mentioned leak types (small/medium/large) are further elaborated with respect to the hazard. In addition, it is also described to what extent the location of the leak influences the hazard and the effect of the hazard.

Table 3: The leak openings leading to different types of leaks.

Network pressure	Diameter of leak opening [mm]		
	8 bar	4 bar	100 mbar
Type Leakage			
Small	< 0.05	< 0.07	< 0.191
Medium	< 1.6	< 2.1	< 6.0
Large	> 1.6	> 2,1	> 6.0

Calculation assumptions: Atmospheric outflow with 100% hydrogen and a gas temperature of 15°C.

4.1 Effects of a small leakage (<0.05 m³/h)

A small leakage has a maximum outflow of 0.05 m³ per hour or 50 litres per hour. There are various causes for this type of leak, such as corrosion or an incorrectly mounted connection. The hazards that can arise from a small leakage outside a building are explained below. As previously mentioned, these are the hazards to which a technician can be exposed.

4.1.1 Approaching a small leakage

When approaching a small leakage³ the dangers are minimal.

4.1.2 Repairing a small leakage

- Fire: When excavating the leak and carrying out the work afterwards, a small flame of up to 5 cm may occur in an unlikely event (see Figure 5). The direct effect of this flame on the technician will be minimal. This flame may cause burns to the technician. However, at a later stage this flame may melt any plastic gas pipe that may be present, creating a larger hole and worsening the fire.

³When approaching a leak it will not always be known whether it is a small or medium leak. Therefore work may only be carried out at gas concentrations < 10% LFL.

Figure 5: Flame length at 100% and flow in L/min (50 L/h \approx 1 L/min), image from [9]

- A free gas outflow in the event of a small leakage does not pose a danger to the technician. A small leakage in the outside air cannot lead to a flammable mixture, as there is sufficient ventilation. This is also evident from measurements taken in a work pit [10]. In this case, a maximum measurement value of 32% LFL was measured for an outflow of 0.29 m³/h of hydrogen for half an hour. The largest number of measurements was less than 10% LFL. Practical research [11] shows that no flammable mixtures can occur in meter cupboards with outflows of up to 0.05 m³/h if there is natural ventilation. If this leaking gas ends up in a ventilated crawl space, it is expected that this will not lead to flammable mixtures.

4.2 Effects of a medium sized leakage (up to 50 m³/h)

In the case of a medium leakage, the most common causes are corrosion or ageing, installation errors or point loads. Leaks close to a facade can also cause leaking of gas to a building/crawl space.

4.2.1 Approaching a medium sized leakage

The flammable hydrogen cloud (area >100% LFL) that is created in a large leak is larger than the flammable cloud with natural gas. This is the conclusion of the report "Flaring and venting of hydrogen" [4]. As with natural gas, the safe distance downwind will also be larger than upwind.

- Fire at ground level: Underground natural gas leaks can be ignited at ground level by using weed burners, for example. This usually results in small flames, and as far as is known, there have never been any incidents involving injury (source: Safety Indicator). A similar situation can occur if hydrogen leaks. The resulting flame cannot penetrate into the ground, as there is insufficient oxygen in the soil for this. Research [5] [12] has shown that hydrogen displaces any air present in the soil, which means that no mixture of gas and air will form in the soil. However, a flame at ground level during (excavation) work can be a potential source of ignition.
- In the event of free gas escape from a medium-sized leakage in the outside air, a flammable gas cloud can be expected over a length of 1.5 to 4 m [4]. If this is ignited, it can lead to burns and/or hearing damage for the technician.
- In the case of free gas outflow from a medium-sized leak, the chance of accumulation to a flammable mixture in enclosed spaces is possible. For example, a crawl space where leaking gas ends up or a distribution box for electricity/telecom. Practical research [11] shows that with outflows of more than 0.1 m³/h in a meter cupboard, gas concentrations greater than 100% LFL occur. Outside the meter cupboard, concentrations of >100% LFL can occur with an outflow from 0.3 m³/h. When approaching these leaks, injuries as a result of an explosion due to flying parts can occur.

4.2.2 Repairing a medium sized leakage

- **Fire:** A medium-sized leakage can lead to a fire in the event of direct ignition. The effects of the burning flare that occurs in an 8 bar pipe have been investigated by the Dutch Institute for Physical Safety (IFV) using simulations in HyRAM and are shown in Table 4. At 50 m³/h, the corresponding leak opening is 1.6 mm (Table 3). This leads to a flare with a length between 0.4 and 0.8 m. The heat load for smaller fires (flares) has not been investigated in the IFV study, but will be lower for a medium-sized leak than the distances at a larger flow rate (hole size 10 and 20 mm). See 5.1 for a further explanation of the heat load 3 kW/m² and 10 kW/m².

Table 4: The effects of a hydrogen fire in the event of a leakage (4.5 to 7,000 m³/h) in an 8 bar pipe. [13]

Hole size (mm)	Flare length (m)	Distance to 3 kW/m ² (m)	Distance to 10 kW/m ² (m)
Line pressure 8 bar			
20	8	11	9
10	4,1	5	4,3
5	2		
2	0,8		
1	0,4		
0,5	0,21		

- **Free outflow and delayed ignition:** A medium-sized leakage can also lead to flammable mixtures in work pits. During measurements in work pits, hydrogen concentrations of 12 vol.-% were measured at an outflow of 15.5 m³/h. At an outflow of 80 m³/h, this increased to 55 vol.-%. [10]. This can cause an explosion in the event of delayed ignition. DNV, commissioned by Enexis, performed calculations [14] into the delayed ignition of a hydrogen cloud in the event of excavation damage. However, the data from this calculation are not suitable for use in this report due to other assumptions (including max. 5 m³/h).
- **Suffocation:** The risk of suffocation when approaching a failure is not considered to be realistic if work is carried out in accordance with VIAG.

In the case of medium-sized leakages, the risk of ignition is realistic if no additional control measures are taken.

4.3 Effects of large leakage (from 50 m³/h)

- **Fire:** During excavation damage where large leaks occur, there are usually also ignition sources present, such as electric tools (reciprocating saw) or an excavator. In addition, the interviews revealed that in case of an excavation damage to the gas pipeline, the electricity cables are regularly damaged as well. This often results in a fire due to the spark formation during this damage. In the case of large hydrogen leakages, the chance of ignition is greater than with natural gas. This is confirmed in the study by Ruiz-Tagle et al. [2], partly due to the lower ignition energy and the broader flammability limits of hydrogen compared to natural gas. At present, the role of static in gas distribution is not yet sufficiently clear. Literature [15] [16] showing that venting H₂ under (very) high pressure can lead to spontaneous ignition of hydrogen. This probably occurs as a result of friction and/or staticity. Under very specific circumstances, staticity can build up as a result of friction with a plastic pipe wall during the movement of gas at high speed. Because the pipe is always carrying gas and does not contain air during daily operation, any static discharge cannot lead to ignition. To what extent this

can occur, for example, when venting hydrogen is not clear at this time. As part of HyDelta 4, further research will be conducted into the role of staticity .

- Free gas outflow: A major danger in the event of a large leakage is the formation of a gas cloud that ignites at a later time. This can cause a pressure wave and a heat load. During tests [17] in the context of Hydelta 2 with direct ignitions of flow rates up to 6,000 Nm³/h and delayed ignitions up to 3,200 Nm³/h, no increased pressure waves were observed. The maximum heat load at a distance of 2 metres is 14 kW/m². A safety distance of 10 metres is recommended (heat radiation < 1.6 kW/m²).
- Suffocation: The risk of suffocation when approaching a failure is not considered realistic if work is carried out in accordance with VIAG.

In previous chapters and paragraphs, the causes of the leaks have been named, a classification of the leak size has been established and the hazards with associated consequences for the technician have been determined. Depending on the situation of the network (for example 8 bar network or 100 mbar network) there are different risks. The effects of six predetermined situations have been determined. These are shown schematically in Appendix A. These tables also include whether the effects for the technician are different for hydrogen compared to natural gas.

Derived from these tables it follows that in the case of a medium or large leakage the risks with hydrogen are always higher. For these reasons additional measures are necessary when approaching and repairing the leak. This is explained in the next chapter.

5 Safety distances

This chapter first provides a general explanation of safety distances (5.1). It then describes what this means for the safety distances to be used in the event of a leakage that ends up in the outside air. The final paragraph provides an explanation of the safety distances in the event of a leak in a distribution pipe that leads to a build-up of gas in a building.

5.1 General

Safety distances have a wide range of purposes in gas transport and gas distribution. At all times, a safety distance is intended to protect bystanders (such as the public, network operator employees and emergency services) from a potential threat. This may include heat load as a result of a fire, detonation pressure when a gas cloud is ignited and flying debris as a result of a detonation. Safety distances can also be considered with the aim of staying outside a gas cloud with a certain gas concentration (for example 100% or 10%). This is because these gas clouds can pose a potential threat (fire or explosion)

Another line of thought is that the object or situation (such as a gas station, an underground pipeline or a work pit) is protected from bystanders, which is not what is meant here.

When assessing the potential threat in the event of gas leaks, the location-specific risk and the fire attention area are taken as the starting point. These assessments then relate to the heat load of a hydrogen fire and the chance of death (also called lethality). Three scales are usually used for this, where 3 kW/m² is the limit for deployment of the fire brigade, 10 kW/m² is the limit for 1% lethality and 35 kW/m² is the limit for 100% lethality, always for an exposure time of 20 seconds [13].

NEN1059:2019, table 2 describes the required safety distances for various objects. These distances are specific to natural gas and the standard is currently being updated to make it suitable for hydrogen.

VIAG-VWI-G36, [18] table 2 explains which safety distances apply when considering a natural gas leakage. This table shows the relationship between pressure, diameter and safety distance. The heat radiation emitted by a hydrogen flame is low due to the absence of carbon (which can cause heat-radiating soot particles) and due to the presence of heat-absorbing water vapour in the flame (HySafe, 2009). Hydrogen flames therefore retain their heat and are very hot compared to hydrocarbon flames.

In 2021, the NIPV studied hydrogen flare fires using HyRAM software [13]. This software can be used to estimate the heat load of a flare fire. Within “NaturalHy” [19] a similar calculation has also been made for radiant heat and lethality in high-pressure pipelines. Much theoretical research relates to hydrogen at high pressure, such as transport pipelines or hydrogen tanks. The H21 study looked at safety distances in relation to gas distribution [20]. In paragraph 4.4.3 of the report for “phase 2” a table is presented for safety distances that are relevant to the sector. A direct comparison is made with natural gas and it is noticeable that in many scenarios the distances are unchanged. The table presented assumes safety distances as operational safety distances and so-called evacuation distances.

Every activity with hazardous substances involves risks. In order to better visualize the risks of these activities for the environment, various calculation packages have been prescribed by the RIVM. This involves software packages such as Safeti-NL, Carola or RBM-II [21]. In a new edition of Safeti-NL, an update has been made for estimating risks in the event of a hydrogen flare fire [22].

The results of these calculations can be translated into scenario maps, for example, as published on the NIPV website [23]. Various scenarios for hydrogen have been calculated, such as a hydrogen boiler in a home, a low-pressure hydrogen pipeline in the street [24] or a flare fire. The scenario of delayed ignition is often not included in these analyses.

Figure 6: Scenario map of a low-pressure hydrogen pipeline in the street

The explanation in this paragraph mainly provides insight into the variables in calculating safety distances. Much of the available information relates to theoretical modelling and not to practical experiments. Heat radiation and lethality are the most important parameters in the analysis.

5.2 Safety distance in case of a leakage in the open air

For practical measurement results and simulations, previous reports of research conducted by Kiwa were considered. In the report “Flaring and blowing off hydrogen” [4] measurements were performed on the heat radiation and the gas concentrations at the outflow of different scenarios for 10, 100 and 300 m³/h.

As part of HyDelta 2.0, venting and flaring up to 6,000 m³/h [17] was assessed with radiant heat, noise, NO_x, contours of the flare, direct ignition and delayed ignition as points of attention. This report advises to maintain a safety distance of at least 10 metres based on the measured heat load, the noise level and the absence of the pressure wave during delayed ignition.

Both HyDelta 2.0 and HyDelta 3.0 have investigated the use of inflatable gas stoppers for hydrogen [10]. In these studies the gas concentration in the work pit was mapped for various gas flows. The current practice in the Netherlands with regard to observing safety distances for natural gas mainly concerns the 10% LFL limit, the 100% LFL limit and heat radiation.

With these principles, a translation of measurements into practical applicability is desirable. In the case of a free outflow of gas, there is always the possibility of a build-up of gas concentrations and therefore a portable gas detection (with both an H₂ and O₂ sensor) must be taken along when a technician goes on site. If hydrogen has not yet been ignited, work can be carried out safely if the gas concentration at the location in question remains below the 10% LFL limit.

In Chapter 3 of this report, outflows are categorised into three classes; small (< 0.05 m³/h), medium (< 50m³/h) and large (> 50m³/h). The table below summarises the main distances (with reference). The distances mentioned for a gas cloud 10% LFL, a gas cloud 100% LFL, the heat load and delayed ignition are related to gas leakages directly into the open-air. The distance with respect to debris and glass is related to gas leakages where the gas enters a building. For the sake of completeness, the latter has already been included here. A further explanation of gas leakages in buildings is included in 5.3.

Table 5 Overview of safety distances related to the different potential threats

Leakage	Leakage rate (m ³ /h)	Distance gas cloud 10% LFL	Distance gas cloud 100% LFL	Heat radiation Max 3 kW/m ²	Flying debris/glass	Pressure due to delayed ignition in the outside air
Small	< 0.05	none	none	none	none	none
Medium	< 50	approximately 16 meters	approximately 3 meters	approximately 3 meters	50 to 70 meters	about 10 meters
Large	> 50	> 16 meters	> 3 meters	10 meters*	50 to 70 meters	10 meters**
Large	100	approximately 20 meters	approximately 4 meters	10 meters	50 to 70 meters	10 meters
Comments						
In the case of a large leakage, the leakage rate of 100 m ³ /h is also specified because the distance to gas clouds is specified in reference [4].						
Source distance 10% LFL		[4]				
Source distance 100% LFL		[4]				
Source distance heat radiation		[17] Heat radiation at medium leakage rate based on figure 24 from [17] *flow rate < 6,000 m ³ /h				
Source distance rubble / glass		[25] [7] (see 5.3 for further explanation)				
Source distance delayed ignition		[17] ** flow rate < 3,200 m ³ /h Medium leakages; no measurement results available. Safety distance equal to a large leak is used.				

5.3 Safety distance in case of gas accumulation in a building

In the event of a gas leak in or near a building, there is a possibility that gas will accumulate in a nearby building. This may involve the entire building itself or parts of the building such as the crawl space.

A safe distance when working near (and outside) a building where gas has accumulated is 50 to 70 metres. This is the distance over which glass can still cause injury (see 3.3) or break. This last aspect is further substantiated in this paragraph. The other effects (heat load, pressure wave and other flying building parts) with possible injury as a result can occur at a distance of less than 50 metres. This safety distance applies to medium and large leakages.

In the case of hydrogen, various studies have been carried out in the context of Hy4heat on the accumulation of gas in a space [26]. This information has been taken over by the NIPV, which is described in one of the scenario books "hydrogen boiler in home".

Based on Hy4heat research, [26] the main conclusions for different outlet locations in a typical British home (for example, in British homes the central heating boiler is often located in a cupboard in the kitchen), excluding cellars and crawl spaces, are summarised:

Hydrogen spreads in a similar way to natural gas.

- Leakages of more than 20 m³/hour can cause hydrogen concentrations of more than 20 vol.-% in the home, but relatively small leakages in a closed environment such as a meter cupboard can also lead to very high hydrogen concentrations locally. A DNVGL report [27] indicates that hydrogen concentrations of more than 10 vol.-% can be expected for leakages of 6-18 m³/hour (100 – 300 l/min) in crawl spaces and meter cupboards.
- Leakages smaller than 20 m³/hour can sometimes also lead to hydrogen concentrations of more than 20 vol.-% in the space where the leakage occurs. This is the case, for example, if there is insufficient ventilation and doors are closed.
- If the doors of the room in which the leakage occurs are open, the hydrogen concentrations in the rest of the house do not exceed 13 vol%. If the doors of the room are closed, the hydrogen concentrations in the rest of the house are generally lower than 10 vol%.
- The higher the outflow in a space, the higher the maximum hydrogen concentrations in the hydrogen layers under a ceiling (see e.g. CFD hydrogen house [28] and HyDelta 2.0, WP6A [29]).

A gas explosion that causes a house to collapse is rare, but it does occur a few times a year in the Netherlands in the case of natural gas. Most victims will occur when houses collapse due to the explosion. If three houses collapse, on average 6 to 7 people will be (fatally) injured, [7] with primary injury and secondary injury (death due to collapse is primary injury and injuries due to debris/flying glass are secondary injury). For five houses, that is 10 people. People who are outside can be hit by flying debris or glass shards.

At hydrogen concentrations below 15 vol.-% the explosion is not powerful enough [6]. People will suffer burns if they are in the room where the explosion takes place.

When gas builds up, a pressure wave will occur upon ignition. For insight into such a situation, scenario maps from the NIPV can be used, such as "Hydrogen boiler in home". The map makes a link with the scenario map for "Hydrogen cylinder package – Explosion" where, just like in a building, pressure can build up.

The figure below shows the consequences of different overpressures.

Figure 7: The NIPV scenario map “Hydrogen Cylinder Pack – Explosion” shows which effects should be taken into account

The percentages given in the table above for victims are secondary. Directly becoming a victim of overpressure, such as through lung damage, is not a determining factor for the injury. Indoors, the injury is mainly caused by splintering (from windows) and the collapse of buildings and walls. Outdoors, the fatal injury is mainly caused by a combination of debris, fragments and knocking over of objects present, resulting in brain damage. Debris and fragments can cause injury at a greater distance than is included in the casualty percentages [25].

For the sake of readability of the table, the limit values for material and personal damage have been equalised. For the classification of damage to objects, slightly different limit values are actually used. The values 0.3 = 0.35 bar and 0.2 = 0.17 bar.

6 With the right control measures, the risk level can remain the same

When working on the current natural gas network, the VIAG-work-instructions (general Dutch safety instructions for distribution system companies and their subcontractors) are used. For the ongoing pilot projects at the Dutch network operators, these safety instructions have been adapted per network operator to work with hydrogen. A number of changes have been implemented for working safely with hydrogen. There are minor differences between the instructions per network operator, which are not considered here. Below an overview is listed of the most important differences between working with hydrogen compared to working with natural gas.

For this report, the hydrogen VWI's (work instructions) of Liander and Enexis were compared with the existing VIAG-VWI's that relate to (securing/solving) leaks. This revealed a number of differences:

- If the source of a gas leakage cannot be located quickly enough, the affected section of pipe must first be depressurised.
- If more than 0.4 vol.% hydrogen is measured inside a building, the entire service line must first be depressurised.
- Before any installation work can be carried out on a hydrogen pipe, the concerning pipe section must first be flushed with nitrogen.

In response to the results from chapter 2 to 5, the following additions to the existing hydrogen VWI's are recommended:

- In addition to the use of gas detection equipment, locations where a possible hydrogen leakage may occur should also be approached with a thermal imaging camera to make any invisible flames visible and prevent the technician from being burned.
- Do not allow temporary repairs due to greater risks in the event of direct outflow.
- In the case of audible and visible leakage, the pipeline must always be depressurized and flushed with nitrogen before work can be carried out on a hydrogen pipeline. When flushing, flushing must be done towards the leak, this can also mean that in the case of a large leak, flushing must be done from both sides of the leak.
- In case of leakages where excavation work is necessary, the gas concentration must be measured at all times at 0.5 meters above ground level and 0.5 meters above the bottom of the excavation. If gas concentrations of more than 10% LFL are measured, the pipe must first be depressurized and degassed by flushing with nitrogen.
- In the event of a build-up of gas in a confined space (such as a building), the gas supply must be stopped at a considerable distance. For example, by setting inflatable gas stoppers or operating shut-off valves. Flying glass is considered the greatest risk of injury. A safety distance of 50 to 70 metres is recommended for this, see Figure 3.
- The greatest risk when restoring the gas supply in the natural gas network after an interruption is an unprotected cooking appliance that is still open when the gas supply is restored [30]. In this way, a flammable mixture (with natural gas) can develop. By law, all new combustion appliances must have flame supervision device. In addition, all natural gas appliances currently on the market are not suitable for a supply of 100% hydrogen. If it is therefore decided to supply a distribution network with 100% hydrogen, all natural gas appliances in the area concerned will have to be replaced. As a result, it is not possible for an appliance without flame supervision device to be present in the hydrogen network and the greatest risk of a flammable mixture developing when restoring the gas supply after an interruption is eliminated. Therefore, restoring the gas supply after a failure with hydrogen could take place with a much lower risk and, in the event of calamities, larger areas could also be disconnected from hydrogen with less risk.

- In the event of (possible) ingress of air that occurs during the leakage or its resolution, the pipe section must always be vented by first flushing it with nitrogen.
- In the event of a gas fire in case of a large leak, a safety distance of at least 10 metres must be maintained.
- Due to the possibility of injury from flying glass in the event of an explosion within a building, a safety distance of 50 to 70 metres must be maintained.
- When carrying out repair and maintenance work, gas detection equipment with at least an H₂ and O₂ sensor should be worn.

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Appendix A: Overview tables of leakage situations

Situation		Main line 8 bar steel ≤ DN 150				
Type of leak						
Cause	Leak size	Can leak gas enter the building (yes/no)	Hazard with H ₂ at approaching incident	Hazard with H ₂ at solving incident*	Effect of hazard at H ₂ for technician**	Effect with H ₂ different from NG
corrosion / ageing	medium	no	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion
excavation damage	large	no	fire, explosion, suffocation	fire, explosion	very severe	yes, during explosion and suffocation
installation errors	medium	no	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion and suffocation
ground movement	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
point load	na.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.

* pipeline without pressure, but not without gas ** when approaching and/or fixing the fault

Situation		Main line 8 bar High Pressure Delivery Set (inlet PE or steel)				
Type of leak						
Cause	Leak size	Can leak gas enter the building (yes/no)	Hazard with H ₂ at approaching incident	Hazard with H ₂ at solving incident*	Effect of hazard at H ₂ for technician**	Effect with H ₂ different from NG
corrosion / ageing	medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion
excavation damage	large	no, not realistic	fire, explosion, suffocation	fire, explosion	very severe	yes, during explosion and suffocation
installation errors	medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion
ground movement	large	yes	fire, explosion, suffocation	fire, explosion	very severe	yes, during explosion and suffocation
point load	medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion

* pipeline without pressure, but not without gas ** when approaching and/or fixing the fault

Situation		Main line 4 bar PE ≤ DN 100				
Type of leak						
Cause	Leak size	Can leak gas enter the building (yes/no)	Hazard with H ₂ at approaching incident	Hazard with H ₂ at solving incident*	Effect of hazard at H ₂ for technician**	Effect with H ₂ different from NG
corrosion / ageing	medium	no	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion
excavation damage	large	no	fire, explosion, suffocation	fire, explosion	very severe	yes, during explosion and suffocation
installation errors	medium	no	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion
ground movement	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
point load	medium	no	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion

* pipeline without pressure, but not without gas ** when approaching and/or fixing the fault

Situation		Main line 100 mbar PE ≤ DN 200				
Type of leak						
Cause	Leak size	Can leak gas enter the building (yes/no)	Hazard with H ₂ at approaching incident	Hazard with H ₂ at solving incident*	Effect of hazard at H ₂ for technician**	Effect with H ₂ different from NG
corrosion / ageing	small or medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion
excavation damage	large	yes	fire, explosion, suffocation	fire, explosion	very severe	yes, during explosion and suffocation
installation errors	small or medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion
ground movement	large	yes	fire, explosion, suffocation	fire, explosion	very severe	yes, during explosion and suffocation
point load	small or medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion

* pipeline without pressure, but not without gas ** when approaching and/or fixing the fault

Situation		Main line 100 mbar PVC ≤ DN 100				
Type of leak						
Cause	Leak size	Can leak gas enter the building (yes/no)	Hazard with H ₂ at approaching incident	Hazard with H ₂ at solving incident*	Effect of hazard at H ₂ for technician**	Effect with H ₂ different from NG
corrosion / ageing	small or medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion
excavation damage	large	yes	fire, explosion, suffocation	fire, explosion	very severe	yes, during explosion and suffocation
installation errors	small or medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion
ground movement	large	yes	fire, explosion, suffocation	fire, explosion	very severe	yes, during explosion and suffocation
point load	small or medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion

* pipeline without pressure, but not without gas ** when approaching and/or fixing the fault

Situation		Service line 100 mbar PE ≤ DN 25				
Type of leak						
Cause	Leak size	Can leak gas enter the building (yes/no)	Hazard with H ₂ at approaching incident	Hazard with H ₂ at solving incident*	Effect of hazard at H ₂ for technician**	Effect with H ₂ different from NG
corrosion / ageing	small or medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion
excavation damage	large	yes	fire, explosion	fire, explosion	very severe	yes, during explosion
installation errors	small or medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion
ground movement	large	yes	fire, explosion	fire, explosion	very severe	yes, during explosion
point load	small or medium	yes	fire	fire, explosion	injury with absence	yes, during explosion

* pipeline without pressure, but not without gas ** when approaching and/or fixing the fault

Possible leakages (small, medium or large) and an explanation of the effects at the different network pressures per cause.

Network pressure		8 bar			4 bar			100 mbar		
Type of leak		small	medium	large	small	medium	large	small	medium	large
Needed diameter of leak opening [mm]		<0.05	<1.6	>1.6	<0.07	<2.1	>2.1	<0.191	<6.0	>6.0
Location of leak		n.a.	Near buildings less common	Near buildings less common	n.a.	Near buildings less common	Near buildings less common	Possible nearby buildings	Possible nearby buildings	Possible nearby buildings
Cause	Corrosion/ageing	n.a.	V	V	n.a.	V	V	V	-	-
	Hydrogen embrittlement	n.a.	V	-	n.a.	V	-	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	Excavation damage	n.a.	-	V	n.a.	-	V	-	V	V
	Installation errors	n.a.	V	-	n.a.	V	-	V	V	-
	Ground movement	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	-	-	V
	Point load	n.a.	V	-	n.a.	V	-	V	V	-
Effect		n.a.	Fire, explosion	Fire, explosion, suffocation	n.a.	Fire, explosion	Fire, explosion, suffocation	Fire	Fire	Fire, explosion, suffocation
Chance of ignition		n.a.	Possible	To be expected	n.a.	Possible	To be expected	Unlikely, but possible in the long term	Unusual (but possible)	Possible
Chance of entering a house		n.a.	Small	Small	n.a.	Small	Small	Possible	Possible	Possible
Hazard with H₂ increased?		n.a.	Yes	Yes	n.a.	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

V = Possibility of type of leakage at given causes
- = This type of leakage is not realistic at the relevant pressure and cause

Appendix B: Other lessons learned from the interviews

During the interviews with technicians and other employees of the grid operator, a number of points emerged that are not a direct addition to this study, but are worth mentioning for possible follow-up research.

Water in the gas pipe

Water can enter the gas pipeline for various reasons. This can lead to problems with the gas supply, especially in areas where the pipeline is at different heights. But sand or other contamination can also enter the pipeline through flushing. A technical manual has been drawn up for natural gas [31] on how to deal with water-ingress leaks. This technical manual will have to be revised for hydrogen.

Solving unexpected situations with hydrogen using knowledge of natural gas

During the interviews, a concern emerged among a number of technicians about the other working methods for hydrogen. If an unexpected situation occurs with hydrogen, for example with unintended gas leakage, it is possible that a technician takes steps that are normal with natural gas. However, this can lead to dangerous situations with hydrogen, partly because of the lower ignition energy and the wider ignition limits. Writing modified work instructions is then not enough, especially in the beginning while hydrogen is not worked with daily/weekly. Following sufficient (repetitive) training and making people aware of the properties of hydrogen is essential here.

Home automation (e.g. smart plugs) may provide more potential ignition sources.

In buildings, more and more electronics are becoming 'smart'. In other words, online control of lamps, curtains, devices and much more. Because this can also be done partly automatically, there is doubt whether this provides more potential ignition sources. Certainly in combination with the lower required ignition energy for hydrogen.

Smellability

Many failures are also reported via gas smell reports (certainly in higher pressures >1 bar and outside areas). In the interviews, the question was asked several times how hydrogen can be smelled compared to natural gas. Research has been [32] done on this before, and the conclusion is that it takes longer for a hydrogen leakage to be detected above ground by smell compared to natural gas. It takes about 40 hours for a small natural gas leakage (5 litres per hour) to be smelled above ground, for hydrogen this can take up to 100 hours. This is because natural gas contains many other substances that are also absorbed by the soil and the soil is therefore saturated more quickly.

Appendix C: What is hydrogen?

Hydrogen is a flammable gas, just like natural gas, but it is very different in many ways. This chapter shows the main differences in properties between natural gas and hydrogen.

Physical and chemical properties

The properties of natural gas and hydrogen differ. This affects the design, management and safety of the distribution network.

- **Molecular structure and density** : Hydrogen (H_2) is the lightest molecule and has a density that is approximately eight times lower than that of natural gas (CH_4). This means that hydrogen rises faster in an atmospheric environment and more hydrogen gas escapes through a leak than an identical leak in natural gas. Depending on the size of the leak, between 1.2 and 3 times more hydrogen will flow out. However, if a pipe is leak-tight for natural gas, it will also be leak-tight for hydrogen.
- **Energy content per volume** : Natural gas has a higher energy density per unit volume than hydrogen. The rule of thumb is that natural gas contains three times as much energy per m^3 than hydrogen. However, because there is a turbulent flow in the distribution network, three times more hydrogen will flow through a pipe. As a result, the amount of energy supplied at a connection remains approximately the same. The three times higher flow rate for hydrogen has no effect on the pressure loss or noise production.
- **Ignition and combustion limits** : Hydrogen has wider flammability limits (between 4 vol.-% and 75 vol.-% gas in air) and requires less ignition energy to ignite than natural gas over a large part of this limit. In practice this means that a discharge of static electricity through clothing, for example, can have sufficient energy to ignite a hydrogen/air mixture between 7 vol.-% and 55 vol.-%.
- **Flame speed** : The speed at which a flame spreads through a gas/air mixture also varies. The flame of natural gas has a speed of approximately 0.37m/s, that of hydrogen is 2.9m/s. This is almost eight times as fast. This is also the reason that hydrogen ignitions are often accompanied by more noise and a larger pressure wave, especially if the ignition takes place in a closed space.
- **Flame image** : The flame image of hydrogen is also different from natural gas. A hydrogen flame is virtually invisible when it burns cleanly. The flame can only become visible if pollution is burned during combustion, for example in the case of excavation damage where the gas flows out at high speed and sand particles enter the flame. In addition, a humid ambient air will also make a hydrogen flame visible.

Risk effect of hydrogen

Inflammation

A hydrogen flame has a lower heat radiation than a natural gas flame. But this does not mean that a hydrogen flame is less dangerous. The radiant heat of a hydrogen flame is lower than natural gas, but the chance that hydrogen ignites is greater. Particularly because of the lower ignition energy (at a specific gas/air ratio) and wider ignition limits. In addition, there is the effect of a delayed ignition, in which a cloud of hydrogen gas can ignite. Due to the higher flame speed, the forces associated with a delayed ignition are also greater.

Suffocation

There is also a risk of suffocation with hydrogen, as it displaces air just like with natural gas. In addition, three times as much gas can flow from the same leak, which can ensure that a dangerous situation is reached more quickly. In addition, in the case of hydrogen distribution, nitrogen is also used in most cases to flush a pipe. The risk of suffocation is particularly present there because nitrogen has approximately the same density as air, and therefore dilutes less in a work pit. Particularly under windless conditions.

Distribution of hydrogen in the soil

If a gas pipeline has a leak, hydrogen will spread in the soil about as far as natural gas. This is the result of a study by performing practical tests and computer calculations [32]. This study also showed that the hydrogen concentration in the soil is lower than with natural gas. While more hydrogen gas flowed from the same leak (approximately 2.4 more outflow). This is mainly because the viscosity (the stickiness) of hydrogen is much lower. In other words: it finds a way up more easily.